

ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF VULNERABILITY TO HIV IN THE FEMALE POPULATION: Review of Scope and Method by Walker and Avant

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Abstract

Objectives: To analyze, in the literature, the concept of vulnerability to the Human Immunodeficiency Virus in women according to the method proposed by Walker and Avant. **Methods:** The concept of interest will be evaluated based on a scoping review, from the perspective of published studies identified in the databases: Embase, Medline, Lilacs and Cinahl . The controlled descriptors of MeSH “Health Vulnerability ” and HIV and of DeCS “Vulnerabilidade em saúde” AND HIV will be inserted in the search fields.

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Descriptors: Health Vulnerability; HIV; Women; Gender Health; Concept Formation.

Introduction

Vulnerability to infection by the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) remains a challenge for public agencies and society because its transmissibility involves social, behavioral and structural factors in the incidence of cases. ^(1,2) HIV permeates various contexts, however the literature emphasizes that priority groups are affected unequally, with higher prevalence and risk behavior in some subgroups. ⁽²⁾

Gender issues have marked changes in the epidemiological profile of this infection, including groups that did not perceive themselves at risk of acquiring the disease, such as heterosexual women who are married or in a stable union. ⁽³⁾

Epidemiological data show that from 2007 to 2021, 381,793 cases of HIV infection were reported in Brazil, of which 266,360 (69.8%) were men and 115,333 (30.2%) were women. Regarding AIDS cases, from 1980 to June 2021, 688,348 (65.8%) cases of AIDS were recorded in men and 356,885 (34.2%) in women. ⁽⁴⁾

HIV also impacts mortality among women, since worldwide, AIDS-related diseases are the main causes of death among women of reproductive age or pregnant and postpartum women. In Brazil, in 2017, 49% of deaths among women were concentrated in the 25 to 39 age group, resulting in the loss of potential years of life for these women, with HIV/AIDS being one of the main causes identified. ⁽⁴⁾

It is clear, therefore, that there is a need to address the health of the female population from a gender perspective, given that this population experiences contexts that increase their vulnerability to HIV. Therefore, it is understood that the epidemic is the result not only of the pathogenicity of the virus, but of multiple factors that are determinants in the health-disease process. ⁽⁵⁾

The concept of vulnerability has been discussed in the field of public health since the beginning of the history of the HIV/AIDS epidemic in 1980. Its use was presented as an analytical alternative for discussions on the concept of risk, with origins in the epidemiological approach. ⁽⁶⁾

Vulnerability refers to the structural conditions that indicate the “susceptibility” of certain individuals to a given issue. ^(6,7) Each concept has attributes that are the characteristics that compose it, as well as consequences that will determine its applicability. ⁽⁸⁾ Analyzing the concept of vulnerability in its essence is essential to allow epistemological and ethical-legal discussions capable of reaching fundamental reflections and practices for health care for this population.

Given these assumptions, the need for a conceptual analysis of vulnerability to HIV in the female population is highlighted, allowing the process of clarification of useful

concepts for nursing care, which can contribute to health promotion actions and the expansion of nursing knowledge.

From this perspective, this study will aim to analyze the concept of vulnerability to HIV in women in the literature according to the method proposed by Walker and Avant.

Methods

This is a theoretical study based on the conceptual analysis of Walker and Avant (2019), following six of the eight steps proposed by the authors, namely: choice of concept; determination of the objective of the analysis; identification of possible uses of the concept; determination of attributes; identification of the model case; and identification of the antecedents and consequences of the concept. ⁽⁹⁾ These steps were chosen because we understand that they are sufficient to respond to the objective proposed for the study. The exclusion of the other steps does not result in losses for the conceptual analysis proposed here.

In the first stage, the concept must be chosen carefully, since it must reflect an area of interest and preferably be related to the authors' field of work. At this stage, a consensus was reached that the concept of vulnerability would be aligned with our research interests. ⁽⁹⁾

In the stage of determining the objective of the analysis, the purposes of analyzing the concept of vulnerability will be reflected upon. In the stage of identifying possible uses of the concept, a literature review will be carried out. The review will help the authors to validate the final choices of defining attributes and provides the evidence base for concept analysis. ⁽⁹⁾

Having selected the concept of vulnerability to HIV in the female population, a scoping review will be carried out in order to structure the theoretical framework of the research process. The steps of the review will be: determination of the research question; literature search; data evaluation; analysis of results and presentation. The guiding research question for this review will be: What are the antecedents, attributes and consequences associated with vulnerability to HIV in the female population identified in the literature?

Data collection will take place between January and February 2024, using the "CAFe" authentication protocol of the Federal University of Ceará, on the Capes journals platform, and then a search will be carried out in the following databases: Embase (ELSEVIER), Medline (PUBMED), Lilacs and Cinahl (EBSCO). In the search fields, the

controlled descriptors of MeSH “Health Vulnerability ” AND HIV and DeCS “Vulnerabilidade em saúde” AND HIV will be inserted .

The inclusion criteria for the composition of the study corpus will be articles that have in the title or text the phrase vulnerability to HIV in women, in Portuguese, English and Spanish, being complete, free, available and free texts. Dissertations, theses, editorials, letters to the editor, reflective studies, experience reports and projects will be excluded.

To select the studies, three analyses will be carried out: the first consisted of evaluating titles and abstracts; the second consisted of excluding duplicate studies from the first analysis; and, finally, the third analysis consisted of reading the pre-selected studies in full.

From the final sample, the definition of the concept attributes will be carried out. This stage will determine the set of attributes that are most frequently associated with the concept, allowing for a broader and more in-depth view. The defining attributes do not need to be numerous, they are not rigid and should immediately convey the idea of the concept. ⁽⁹⁾

In the model case identification stage, a situation will be described in which the use of the concept and its defining attributes are explicit. The model case should be a pragmatic example that is capable of accurately translating the essence of the concept under study. ⁽⁹⁾ Finally, we will proceed with the identification of the antecedents and consequences of the concept, which contribute to the understanding of the social context in which the concept is used.

A bibliometric analysis of the studies initially found in the Scopus database will be performed to determine the publication profile on the topic, which will assist in the theoretical structuring process. For the analysis, the R software with the biblioshiny package will be used .

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